

THE ROLE OF AGROTECHNOLOGY IN INCREASING THE PRODUCTIVITY OF WHEAT GRAIN

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Abstract

High-yielding varieties adapted to agrotechnological conditions play an important role in increasing the productivity of grain crops. It is known from practice that not all varieties use the conditions created during cultivation in the same way. Some varieties have low productivity, others suffer from various diseases or suffer from unfavorable wintering conditions. This article discusses the role of agrotechnology in increasing the yield of wheat grain.

Keywords. Winter wheat, predecessor, tillage, organic fertilizers, mineral fertilizers.

Аннотация

Большую роль в повышении урожайности зерновых культур играют высокоурожайные сорта, адаптированные к агротехнологическим условиям. Из практики известно, что не все сорта одинаково используют условия, созданные при выращивании. Одни сорта имеют низкую продуктивность, другие болеют различными заболеваниями или страдают от неблагоприятных условий зимовки. В данной статье рассматривается роль агротехники в повышении урожайности зерна пшеницы.

Ключевые слова. Озимая пшеница, предшественник, обработка почвы, органические удобрения, минеральные удобрения.

INTRODUCTION

For production, those that are capable of producing high and stable yields under given conditions are of the greatest value. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of seed production is to correctly place varieties in the natural and ecological zones of our country, taking into account the best adaptation of each variety to local conditions. The main principle for determining the adaptability of a variety to given conditions can be its normal growth and development, ensuring high and stable yields over the years. To obtain a high yield of winter

wheat grain, the right combination of agricultural practices is necessary. Of great importance in the formation of the crop is the correct choice of the predecessor, the method of basic tillage, the use of organic and mineral fertilizers. But the effectiveness of the agricultural practices used largely depends on the prevailing weather and climate conditions of the year. The purpose of this work was to study and evaluate the degree of influence on the yield of winter wheat grains of various agricultural practices in various weather conditions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

With the breeding and introduction of new highly productive and winter-hardy varieties, the further expansion of the sowing of winter wheat in those regions where it occupies a relatively small proportion among winter crops is connected. The introduction of new high-yielding varieties of winter wheat into production will contribute to a sharp rise in grain farming, an increase in labor productivity, a reduction in production costs, and the introduction of progressive methods of agricultural technology.

In order to better use the potential (productivity, grain quality, etc.) inherent in a certain valuable variety, it is necessary to keep it clean at all stages of the selection and seed production process, and to constantly improve the variety and biological characteristics of seeds.

RESULTS

From the practice of agriculture, it is known that with prolonged use and violation of agricultural technology, varietal seeds deteriorate their valuable properties. The most rapid deterioration of a variety and a decrease in its yield occur when it is grown under conditions of low agricultural technology (poor tillage, poor seed quality, mechanical contamination of seeds with other varieties and crops, etc.). The influence of negative factors is gradually increasing, which ultimately leads to the degeneration of the variety, lower yields, deterioration of grain quality and other positive properties. With high agricultural technology, the yield and physical properties of seeds can be preserved for a long time.

Seeds grown in advanced agriculture are distinguished not only by high yield, but also by high viability compared to seeds obtained using traditional agricultural technology. Winter wheat seeds grown in conditions of high agrotechnology give a higher yield of 3-12 centners per hectare than seeds obtained by traditional agricultural technology. When seeds from fertile soil are planted, the yield is 1 to 2.4 centners higher than seeds from medium soil.

CONCLUSION

In some farms, the large difference between the productivity of elite and other reproduction seeds is largely due to the level of agricultural technology. In farms where winter wheat is grown under high agricultural conditions, seed yield and technological quality do not decrease with increase, at least until 5-6 reproductions.

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